

COMPARING SOME IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES WITH THE HELP OF JANE AUSTEN'S BOOK "PRIDE AND PREJUDICE".

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to compare, to analyse and to find idiomatic phrases, metaphors and idioms in "Pride and prejudice" book. Pride and Prejudice is a novel that frequently used idioms with metaphors. For instance, Mary says that they must "stem the tide of malice" (p. 245). The reader understands that Mary is not referring to a literal ocean tide. She is using the word metaphorically. In addition to, it helps to identify what do these idioms mean and how many are there? According to meanings of them they were used coherently in this work, and one by one we will know about their meanings. These idiomatic phrases, metaphors and idioms serve to describe all scenes of work naturally, and they help to understand and to be a page turner. However, when we translate them other languages without knowing the meaning of idioms fully it reacts to readers differently, so while translating we must comb their meanings again and again. It's known that while we are using idiomatic phrases or metaphors there are some similarities and differences between Uzbek and English languages. According to the contexts we mostly use proper idioms when we compose works such as novel.

Key words: Idomatic phrases, metaphors, idioms, analysing, "Pride and Prejudice", translation.

What is idiom?

An idiom is a phrase that, when taken as a whole, has a meaning you wouldn't be able to deduce from the meanings of the individual words. It's essentially the verbal equivalent of using the wrong math formula but still getting the correct answer.

The phrase “kill two birds with one stone” is an example of an idiom. Fluent and native English speakers understand that this doesn’t refer to harming birds or using stones, but that someone is completing two tasks at once.

A group of words built by usage as having a meaning not deducible from those of the individual words (e.g. over the moon, see the light).

What are metaphors?

A figure of speech in which a word or phrase is applied to an object or action to which it is not literally applicable.

Common metaphor examples:

Life is a highway.

Her eyes were diamonds.

He is a shining star.

The snow is a white blanket.

She is an early bird.

INTRODUCTION

English is the most popular and common language in the universe. And there are numerous works which were written in this language by English writers.

One of them is the most page-turner book “Pride and Prejudice” by the author Jane Austen. It describes humans’ pride, difficult situations and problems that are without solutions. It was felt by all readers so positively and translated to a bunch of languages. Furthermore, literary scientists and great translators worked on this work again and again, and they confirmed that work is actually an immaculate masterpiece.

Writer, Jane Austen, used a great deal of idioms in this book to make the work zhoooshing and verily it assists to imagine very effortlessly and perfectly. Here you may perceive some of what: those are transparent idioms, semi-transparent idioms, semi-opaque idioms, and opaque idioms. Transparent idioms are those idioms which are easy to comprehend its constituent meaning. Semi-transparent idioms are the idioms that usually have metaphorical meaning and their constituent parts have a little role in comprehending the whole meaning of the expression. Semi-opaque idioms are the group of idioms whose figurative meaning is not related to the meaning of their constituent words, in other words, the idiomatic expression is separated into two parts; a part with literal meaning, and the other part with a figurative meaning. The last is opaque idioms which is the idioms where the literal meaning of their parts have little to do with actual sense of idiom because it has cultural reference item. Transparent

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EXAMPLES:

- 1) „Let at last“ means finally has been rent.
- 2) „Listening at the door“ means listening to other conversation in Secret.
- 3) „Design in“ means goal/purpose.
- 4) „Good heavens“ means oh god.
- 5) „Poor nerve“ means mentality.
- 6) „Poppy cock“ means non-sensible man/woman.
- 7) „Catch your eye“ means interesting to see.
- 8) „Watch your tongue“ means speaks carefully.
- 9) „The painted peacocks“ means a noble man/ noble woman who like to wear beautiful thing.
- 10) „Take the veil“ means become a nun.
- 11) „Not if I can help it“ means a polite way of saying no/rejection.
- 12) „A long way“ from means different economy status from.
- 13) „Count your blessings“ means be grateful.
- 14) „Let alone“ means let it go.
- 15) „Put paid to it“ means finish something off.

- 16) „Kill it stone dead“ means destroy something utterly.
- 17) „All the world“ means everything.
- 18) „Little standing“ means low status in society.
- 19) „Without a roof over their head“ means have no place to live.
- 20) „Nor a penny to their name“ means have no money/ very poor Person.
- 21) „Six inches deep in mud“ means very dirty.
- 22) „Positively medieval“ means country bumpkin person.
- 23) „My blossom“ means dear.
- 24) „Fall to my lot“ means my job/ duty.
- 25) „Do dote on“ means love or ardently.
- 26) „Not room enough to do them justice“ means have no space.
- 27) „Get in your“ way means get away.
- 28) „For heaven’s sake“ means oh my god
- 29) „The order of the day“ means the important things to do.
- 30) „My humble dwelling“ means a flat house or a standard house.
- 31) „Bound to pay“ means very useful things to do.
- 32) „Captured my special attention“ means interested in.
- 33) „I’m lost“ means have no idea.
- 34) „A laughing stock“ means a bullied person because he/she Always do stupid thing.
- 35) „Owe me a fortune“ means owe a lot of money from other Person.
- 36) „She’s blooming“ means blushing.
- 37) „A credit to his profession“ means honour to job.
- 38) „Poor foot soldier“ means infantry soldier.
- 39) „Cold greeting“ means do not care about each other.
- 40) „Think ill of anybody“ means think bad to a person or more.
- 41) „Twice the man Darcy“ means better than Darcy.
- 42) „Breath-taking“ means spectacular.
- 43) „My lightness of foot“ means a good dancer.
- 44) „To lavish upon one’s partner“ means give so many things to Other person in order to gain their affections.
- 45) „Throw her sisters in the way of other rich men“ means many

Her sisters get other rich man to marry.

- 46) „Snap him up“ means get someone fast.
- 47) „The violence of my affections“ means bad love actions.
- 48) „Headstrong“ means someone who had strong opinion about Something.
- 49) „Little hiccup dealt immediately“ means a small problem to solve Fast.
- 50) „Turned down“ means rejecting.
- 51) „No earthly reason“ means not have a specific reason.
- 52) „Rather grey“ means dull.
- 53) „Quite a slave to your education“ means ignore on education.
- 54) „False modesty“ means pretend holding a humble opinion Oneself to encourage other people.
- 55) „Accepting of my hand“ means ask to marry someone.
- 56) „To the censure of the world for caprice“ means egoism person Who involved in other person matter.
- 57) „Very thin on the ground“ means abundant/ not plentiful.
- 58) „Eaten up“ means thoroughly enjoy something.
- 59) „May I see you back“ means asking to send someone to where She stayed.
- 60) „You had painted him“ means describing other person character To other.
- 61) „Grave indeed“ means also mourned of other person disaster or Experience.
- 62) „Out of their sight“ means uncontrollable.
- 63) „Fallen sister“ means a girl who ruined up her reputation in the Society.
- 64) „Turn us out“ means make someone leave their place.
- 65) „Before he’s cold in his grave“ means someone that has just died.
- 66) „Catch my breath“ means take a rest for a while.
- 67) „Laid on that wretched man“ means depend on someone who Bribed blasted man.
- 68) „A bowl of punch“ means a big feast with fancy.
- 69) „I’ve been so blind“ means not seeing the truth.

70) „No doubt poisoned by his pernicious sister“ means persuaded To choose a bad way by someone close to him.

71) „Took the trouble of coming so far“ means want to solve an Urgent thing immediately.

72) „Not possess equal frankness“ means not the same rude.

73) „Heaven and Earth“ means oh my goodness.

74) „Are the shades of Pemberley to be thus polluted“ means Intermarriage with someone deemed un-worthy.

75) „What on earth“ means what has happened.

76) „Once in your life“ means just for a moment.

77) „Bewitched me, body, and soul“ means in love with me.

78) „Out of your senses“ means crazy or out of mind.

79) „Pay him back“ means repay one“s kindness.

80) „Send them in“ means asking to make someone entering a room.

A bunch of phrases, Idioms and metaphors are given above. As we compare them between two languages, there are some Uzbek idioms in common with English idioms. Examples:

1. “Not if I can help it“ means a polite way of saying no/rejection. “Aybga buyurmaysiz”

2. „To lavish upon one’s partner“ means give so many things to Other person in order to gain their affections. “Laganbardorlik qilish”

3. „Bewitched me, body, and soul“ means in love with me. “Aql-u xushimni yo‘qotdim”

4. “Fallen sister“ means a girl who ruined up her reputation in the society. Hammani oldida “Obro‘yini bir pul qildi”

5. „I’ve been so blind“ means not seeing the truth.“ Ko‘zim ko‘r bo‘lgan ekan”, avvalroq anglamadim.

6. „Poppy cock“ means non-sensible man/woman. -Siz ham ahmoq mulla ekansiz! — dedi Safar bo‘zchi ¹.

7. „Nor a penny to their name“ means have no money/ very poor “Bir tiyinsiz qoldim”

8. „Watch your tongue“ means speaks carefully. “Tilingni tiy” Example:” Tilingni tiy,bola!” ²

9. „Out of their sight“ means uncontrollable. “O‘lgudek qaysar”

These idioms are similar in both languages and we can use them according to the context in Uzbek and English languages vice versa.¹

Nine of eighty English idioms have resemble and proper alternatives in Uzbek language that they are given above.²

CONCLUSION

In this article we compared a bunch of **idioms** and **phrasal verbs** in two languages (Uzbek and English), we would be witness that there are some similarities and differences between both these languages' idioms and cants. Idioms and phrases enrich languages' terminology and vocabulary. Especially, people use these expressions of words orally, not in written way. We cannot utilize these vocabularies in any way, as stated by situation we can use these metaphors in languages reciprocally. In "Pride and Prejudice", Jane Austen used such idioms with great expertness, that is, to give readers a more complete and deeper understanding of the important situation. And from this we can see how skilled writer and true creator Jane Austen is.

¹<https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://uz.m.wiktionary.org/wiki/ahmoq&ved=2ahUKEwixx4nozpt9AhVSpYsKHWrJDJkQFnoECAkQAQ&usg=AOvVaw2IHIEgQ7vZCcS6ciWL04nl> Abdulla Kadiriy from "Mehrobdan chayon"

²[https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://saviya.uz/ijod/dramaturgiya/tanho-qayiq-yoxud-devonaning-orzusi/&ved=2ahUKEwj7fmuzZT9AhWS6CoKHb9sAMsQFnoECA0QAQ&usg=AOvVaw3u5Fu2ZJHXeDFH181K_yE7Erkin A'zam from "Tanho qayiq".](https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://saviya.uz/ijod/dramaturgiya/tanho-qayiq-yoxud-devonaning-orzusi/&ved=2ahUKEwj7fmuzZT9AhWS6CoKHb9sAMsQFnoECA0QAQ&usg=AOvVaw3u5Fu2ZJHXeDFH181K_yE7Erkin A'zam from)

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5. "Pride and prejudice" book by Jane Austen.

